

Targeting cancer cell sialylation with monosaccharide analogues modulates EGFR in colorectal cancer cells[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the leading causes of cancer-related death worldwide, mainly due to resistance to targeted therapies such as Cetuximab, a chimeric monoclonal antibody targeting epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) used in RAS wild-type tumours. Aberrant glycosylation, specifically increased sialylation, has been implicated in tumour progression and therapy resistance. However, its role in the response to EGFR-targeted treatment is not fully understood. This study investigates the impact of inhibition of sialylation on CRC cells' malignant properties and on responsiveness to Cetuximab therapy. Three RAS wild-type CRC cell lines with distinct sialylation profiles, including an ST6GalI overexpressing model, were used as models to evaluate the effects of a pan-sialyltransferase inhibitor. Treatment effectively reduced both terminal α 2,3- and α 2,6-sialylation at the cell surface and induced a global remodelling of the *N*-glycome, with decreased sialylated and increased neutral glycans. Functionally, sialylation significantly impaired cell motility without affecting cell viability in any of the cell models. Total EGFR expression and basal activation were not altered, while EGFR glycosylation was directly modulated, particularly terminal α 2,6-sialylation. Importantly, EGFR sialylation affected Cetuximab binding and receptor activation in a cell line-dependent manner, with cells bearing α 2,6-sialylation showing modified antibody responsiveness. Overall, these findings demonstrate that EGFR sialylation modulates receptor behaviour and Cetuximab response in CRC, highlighting the inhibition of sialylation as a potential strategy to overcome glycosylation-mediated therapeutic resistance.

1. Introduction

Colorectal cancer (CRC) represents a major global health burden, being among the most frequently diagnosed malignancies and one of the leading causes of cancer-related death worldwide [1]. Due to late detection, almost 50% of patients develop metastatic disease, which remains the primary cause of CRC-related death [2]. Current CRC treatment relies on different therapeutic approaches that include surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and targeted therapies, selected

according to disease stage and molecular characteristics of the tumour [3,4]. Molecular profiling has improved patient stratification through the identification of predictive molecular biomarkers [5–7]. Over the past decades, the introduction of targeted approaches, such as monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) directed against specific oncogenic drivers, has significantly improved the clinical outcome of metastatic CRC and highlighted the importance of tumour-specific signalling pathways as therapeutic targets [8,9]. However, the efficacy of these agents is often limited, mainly due to the high heterogeneity of CRC, characterized by

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pronounced inter- and intra-tumoral variability [10]. This feature contributes to the highly variable clinical responses observed in CRC patients. Thus, treatment resistance and limited responsiveness remain major obstacles, underscoring the unmet need for understanding associated molecular cues and for developing complementary therapeutic strategies [11].

The epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) plays an important role in CRC progression by regulating key cellular processes such as proliferation, survival, migration, and invasion [12]. Therefore, EGFR has emerged as an important therapeutic target in CRC. Cetuximab is a chimeric mAb that targets the extracellular domain of EGFR, competing with EGF in binding the subdomain III of the receptor's extracellular region, impairing receptor membrane oligomerization and, therefore, suppressing downstream oncogenic signalling [13]. Although it is currently applied in clinical practice, this targeted therapy is restricted to patients with tumours lacking a mutation that constitutively activates *RAS* genes (*RAS* wild-type) [14]. Even within this genetically selected population, a substantial proportion of *RAS* wild-type CRC patients fail to respond to the treatment or develop resistance during therapy [15,16]. Increasing evidence suggests that post-translational modifications of EGFR, such as protein glycosylation, may influence receptor function, surface accessibility, and antibody binding, thereby contributing to variability in patient response to Cetuximab [17].

Protein glycosylation stands as the most abundant and structurally diverse post-translational modification that critically regulates many physiological processes involved in several pathological conditions [18,19]. In cancer, this process is frequently deregulated, leading to the emergence of tumour-associated glycosylation patterns that contribute to malignant transformation, disease progression, and therapeutic resistance [19,20]. Among cancer-associated glycan alterations, aberrant sialylation is considered a feature of tumour cells and is characterized by increased levels of sialic acid (Neu5Ac) residues [21,22]. In CRC, hypersialylation has been associated with enhanced tumour aggressiveness, immune evasion, and tumour metastasis, and is mainly attributed to altered expression and activity of Golgi-residing sialyltransferases (STs) [23–25]. ST6GalI and ST3GalIV are two major enzymes responsible for the terminal capping of galactose residues with Neu5Ac motifs in α 2,6- and α 2,3- linkages in CRC, respectively [26–28]. The main product of ST6GalI is the terminal α 2,6-linked sialic acid (α 2,6-Neu5Ac) structure in *N*-glycans, and its overexpression is present in different cancers [29]. Increased terminal α 2,6-sialylation is associated with proliferation, invasion, metastasis, angiogenic processes, and epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition [30–33]. On the other hand, ST3GalIV is responsible for α 2,3-linked sialic acid (α 2,3-Neu5Ac) sialylation [34]. Specifically, it has been shown that in many CRC cell lines, ST3GalIV is the main driver of Sialyl Lewis X (SLe^X) biosynthesis in glycoproteins [25]. SLe^X antigen is involved in metastasis, immune evasion, and drug resistance, leading to poor patient survival [35,36].

EGFR is a transmembrane glycoprotein that bears eleven *N*-glycosylation sites in its extracellular region [37,38]. Previous studies have shown that modulating EGFR glycosylation can influence receptor activation, dimerization, intracellular trafficking, and degradation, ultimately impacting intensity and duration of downstream signalling, as well as affecting its localization and stability at the cell surface [39–42]. These features highlight glycan composition as a key determinant of receptor behaviour [43]. Although indirect evidence suggests that sialylation may impact the efficacy of EGFR-targeted therapies, few studies have directly investigated how modulation of sialylation using glyco-engineered models affects EGFR glycosylation and therapeutic antibody binding in CRC [33,44,45]. Given the role of glycosylation, in particular sialylation, the modulation of ST activity has emerged as a potential therapeutic strategy to investigate how glycan remodelling affects malignant properties and therapeutic responses in cancer cells [20,46,47].

Over the past decades, glycan mimetics such as monosaccharide analogues have been developed as chemical tools to modulate glycosylation pathways and interfere with the biosynthesis of aberrant

glycans that drive tumorigenesis [48]. Specifically, chemical modifications introduce a functional group into common monosaccharides, which are recognized by the cells as natural sugars but block enzymatic incorporation or impair glycan elongation, thereby inhibiting specific biosynthetic steps [48]. Among these modifications, the introduction of a fluorine atom is particularly common and one of the most promising in translational studies [49]. In this context, the modification of Neu5Ac, the most common type of sialic acid in humans, has been explored. Specifically, 3F_{ax}-Peracetyl Neu5Ac (3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac), a cell-permeable fluorinated sialic acid analogue, has shown promising results in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models [50]. This cell-permeable analogue, after entering the cell, is metabolically converted into a CMP-Neu5Ac mimetic with a C3 fluorine substituent that competitively inhibits sialyltransferases, and accumulates within the cell, halting the *de novo* synthesis of CMP-Neu5Ac through a feedback loop [51].

In this study, we investigated the impact of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac on terminal sialylation in CRC cell models. We evaluated the impact on both terminal α 2,3- and α 2,6-sialylation, using different CRC cell lines. We further explore its effect on EGFR sialylation and activation, inferring about its potential as a therapeutic strategy in cancer.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Cell lines and treatment

Three human CRC cell lines (COLO205, Caco-2, and SW48) were purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA). The SW48 cell line was previously transfected with the full-length human *ST6GalI* gene (SW48OE cells) [33]. All cell lines were grown in a monolayer in uncoated cell culture flasks, at a temperature of 37 °C in 5% CO₂ atmosphere. Caco-2 and SW48OE cells were cultured in DMEM, high glucose, GlutaMAX™ supplement and pyruvate medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). COLO205 cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 with stable glutamine with 25 mM HEPES medium (Biowest, Nuaille, France). SW48OE cells culture medium was further supplemented with 0,1 mg/mL of hygromycin B gold (InvivoGen, San Diego, CA, USA). All the culture media were supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Biowest).

In all performed assays, cells were seeded in 6-well uncoated plates at a density of 1×10^5 cells/mL in complete growth medium and allowed to adhere for 24 h. Cells were then treated with 100 μ M of 3F_{ax}-Peracetyl Neu5Ac (EMD Millipore Corp., Burlington, MA, USA) for 72 h, in the absence of antibiotic selection.

For functional assays with the anti-EGFR mAb Cetuximab (Erbix, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) cells were seeded in 6-well culture plates at a density of 5×10^5 cells/mL. Cells were allowed to adhere for 24 h in complete growth medium and then treated with 10 μ g/mL Cetuximab for 72 h, in condition medium (1% FBS and absence of selective antibiotic). For Western blot analysis, a 4 h treatment with Cetuximab (10 μ g/mL) followed by 10 min stimulation with 10 ng/mL EGF (Merck Millipore, Burlington, MA, USA) was done before cell lysis.

Untreated cells and cells treated with 0.1% v/v Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO) were used as controls in all the experiments.

2.2. Flow cytometry

Cell surface glycosylation was assessed with antibody and lectin staining using flow cytometry. Cells were detached with Accutase (GRISP, Porto, Portugal), resuspended in fresh medium, and centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 5 min. A total of 1×10^5 cells were washed twice with flow cytometry buffer (phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) with 1% Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA, Merck Millipore) and incubated with primary antibody for SLe^X (CD15s, D1/250, BD Bioscience, Sofia, Bulgaria) or *Sambucus nigra* Agglutinin (SNA) for α 2,6-Neu5Ac (SNA-FITC conjugated, D1/2000, Vector Laboratories, Newark, CA, USA) for 30 min at 4 °C. For SLe^X staining, cells were then washed twice with flow

cytometry buffer and incubated with Alexa Fluor 647 anti-mouse IgM (Jackson ImmunoResearch, West Grove, PA, USA) for 30 min at 4 °C. Negative controls were performed by using unstained cells or cells stained only with secondary antibodies. Cells were washed twice, resuspended in flow cytometry buffer, and labelled with 1 µg/mL 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) prior to analysis. Data acquisition was performed using BD LSRFortessa and analysed with the FlowJo software (BD Biosciences). For all experiments, fluorescence signals were quantified as median fluorescence intensity (MFI), which was used as the primary readout to evaluate changes in marker expression.

2.3. Immunofluorescence assay

All cell lines were seeded in 13 mm coverslips (Marienfeld, Lauda-Königshofen, Germany) in a 24-well plate. Cells were washed with PBS and fixed with Paraformaldehyde 4% for 10 min at room temperature (RT). Cells were then permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X-100 in PBS for 10 min, followed by incubation with 50 mM ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl) in PBS for 10 min to quench residual free aldehydes. Blocking non-specific binding was performed using 10% BSA in PBS at RT for 30 min, followed by primary antibody incubation at 4 °C overnight (ON) for SLe^x detection (CD15s, D1/250, BD Biosciences), or SNA-FITC incubation for 1 h at RT for α₂,6-Neu5Ac detection (D1/2000, Vector Laboratories). Slides were then incubated with fluorescently labelled secondary antibody Alexa Fluor 594 anti-mouse IgM (D1/500 in 5% BSA in PBS, Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) for 1 h at RT. Nuclear counterstaining was performed by incubating cells with DAPI for 10 min, and coverslips were then mounted with VectaShield (Vector Laboratories). The fluorescent signal was examined using a fluorescence microscope, and images were acquired with Zeiss Axio Imager Z1, Zeiss AxioCam MR version 3.0, and the AxioVisionRel (version 4.8) software (Carl Zeiss).

2.4. Filter-aided sample preparation (FASP) tryptic digestion for N-glycofingerprinting

All reagents and chemicals were purchased from Merck KGaA, unless stated otherwise, and were of the highest purity available.

Prior to N-glycans analysis, 100 µg of each cell lysate was digested with trypsin using the FASP protocol as previously described [52] with slight modifications. Accordingly, cell lysates were dried and resuspended in 200 µL of urea buffer (8 M urea in 0.1 M Tris-HCl, pH 8.5). Samples were loaded onto Nanosep™ centrifugal filter units (10 K Omega™ membrane, Pall Corporation, Dreieich, Germany), previously rinsed with 50 µL of urea buffer, and centrifuged at 14,000 ×g for 5 min at RT. The flow-through was discarded.

Subsequently, disulfide bonds were reduced with 100 µL of 40 mM dithiothreitol (DDT) at 56 °C for 20 min, and the -SH groups were alkylated with 100 µL of 55 mM iodoacetamide for 20 min in the dark at RT as reported before [52]. Filters were washed three times with 100 µL of urea buffer and three times with 100 µL of 50 mM ammonium bicarbonate buffer.

Proteins were digested on-filter with trypsin (Promega, Madison, WI, USA) at a 1/50 enzyme-to-substrate ratio in 100 µL of 50 mM ammonium bicarbonate (NH₄HCO₃) buffer containing 5% acetonitrile and 1 mM calcium chloride (CaCl₂) by ON incubation at 37 °C. Peptides were recovered by centrifugation at 8,000 ×g for 7 min, followed by additional washes with digestion buffer and ultrapure water. The combined eluates were dried in a vacuum concentrator (Alpha 2-4 LSC basic coupled to a RVC 2-33 CD plus, Martin Christ GmbH, Osterode am Harz, Germany) and stored at -20 °C until further analysis.

2.5. N-glycofingerprinting: sample preparation and xCGE-LIF-based analysis

Tryptically digested cell lysates were prepared for N-glycofingerprint via multiplexed capillary gel electrophoresis with laser-induced

fluorescence detection (xCGE-LIF) by using the glyXprep™ Sample Preparation Kit (glyXera GmbH, Magdeburg, Germany) as described before [53,54]. Briefly, N-glycans were released from tryptic glycopeptides with the endoglycosidase PNGaseF ON, labelled with 8-aminopyrene-1,3,6-trisulfonic acid (APTS), and purified via hydrophilic interaction chromatography in solid-phase extraction mode (HILIC-SPE), carefully following the kit instructions. Analyses of labelled N-glycans were conducted on a GlycoDecoder™ (glyXera), based on a modified ("glyconeered") 4-capillary 3130 Genetic Analyzer equipped with a 50 cm capillary array filled with POP-7™ polymer. The samples were electrokinetically injected and analysed with a running voltage of 15 kV. Generated glycan data were analysed with the glycoanalysis software glyXtoolCE™ (glyXera), performing migration time alignment to orthogonally double aligned migration time units (MTU™) for peak annotation and a relative quantification by normalization to total peak height (i.e., %TPH). As previously reported, oligosaccharide impurities were removed by combined glucoamylase P and dextranase digestion [55].

2.6. Cell viability assay

Cell viability was measured *in vitro* by the 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) method using a commercially available kit (MTT Cell Proliferation Kit I, Roche, Basel, Switzerland). Cells were seeded for 24 h in triplicate in a 96-well plate at a density of 5 × 10³ cells/well and then treated with 100 µM of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac. Untreated cells, cells treated with 0.1% v/v DMSO, and cells treated with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) were used as negative controls and positive controls, respectively. After 24 h, 48 h, and 72 h, MTT Kit solutions were added to each well according to the manufacturer's instructions (Roche). Fluorescence intensity was measured at 600 nm using Synergy™ Mx microplate reader (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The signal corresponds to the amount of formazan produced by metabolically active cells. Results are presented as means ± Standard Deviation (SD) for each sample, and proliferation levels obtained were normalized and compared to untreated cells.

2.7. Wound healing assay

Cell motility was assessed *in vitro* by a wound healing assay. The 3-well ibidi culture-inserts (ibidi GmbH, Gräfelfing, Germany) were applied to a 12-well plate, and 5 × 10⁴ cells/70 µL were seeded in each compartment of the inserts and left to adhere for 24 h. The insert was then carefully removed, leaving a defined gap area (wound) between the cells. After being washed twice with PBS, cells were treated with 100 µM of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac. Untreated cells and cells treated with 0.1% v/v DMSO were used as a negative control. Cells were then allowed to migrate into the gap area. Images were taken at 0 h, 24 h, and 48 h, at a magnification of 50×.

2.8. Western and far-western blot assays

Cultured cells were washed twice with ice-cold PBS, and lysates were collected directly in Lysis Buffer 17 (R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA), supplemented with a PhosSTOP phosphatase inhibitor cocktail (Roche) and a cOmplete protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche). Total protein concentrations of whole cell lysates were determined using the DC protein assay kit (BioRad, Hercules, CA, USA). Total protein lysates were separated by polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) (EGFR - 5 µg; pEGFR - 20-40 µg; α₂,6-Neu5Ac - 5 µg; SLe^x - 5 µg) and blotted onto nitrocellulose membranes (GE Healthcare, Chicago, IL, USA). Membranes were then blocked with 5% BSA or 5% skimmed milk for 1 h at RT, followed by ON incubation with primary antibodies at 4 °C. Membranes were then washed with PBS-Tween 0.05% and incubated with horseradish peroxidase-labelled secondary antibodies (Jackson ImmunoResearch) for 1 h at RT. For lectin staining, membranes were blocked

with 2% polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) ON at 4 °C. Then, membranes were incubated with biotinylated SNA (D1/3000, Vector Laboratories) for 1 h at RT, followed by incubation with peroxidase-conjugated streptavidin (D1/100 000, GE Healthcare). Specific signals were detected using the enhanced chemiluminescence (ECL) detection method.

The following primary antibodies working dilutions were used: anti-EGFR (clone D38B1, D1/1000, Cell Signalling Technology, Danvers, MA, USA), anti-phosphorylated EGFR (Y1086) (D1/1000, Cell Signalling Technology), SLe^x (D1/500, BD Bioscience), SNA (D1/3000, Vector Laboratories), MAL-I (D1/2000, Vector Laboratories). Anti-β-actin (clone I-19, D1/2000, Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Dallas, TX, USA) was used as a loading control. As secondary antibodies, horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated polyclonal anti-rabbit (D1/25,000) and polyclonal anti-mouse (D1/5000, Jackson ImmunoResearch) were used.

2.9. EGFR immunoprecipitation

Protein G Sepharose Fast Flow beads (GE Healthcare) were washed three times with ice-cold PBS and conjugated with an anti-EGFR antibody (EGFR1, Cell Signalling Technology) for 2 h at 4 °C. In parallel, 500 µg of protein from cell lysates were pre-cleared for 2 h at 4 °C with protein G Sepharose Fast Flow beads washed with ice-cold PBS. EGFR immunoprecipitation was performed by incubating the pre-cleared lysates with the antibody-conjugated beads ON at 4 °C. All conjugation steps were performed with gentle rotation. Antibody-protein bead complexes were washed with ice-cold PBS and ice-cold 0.1% Triton™ X-100 in PBS to eliminate non-specific binding. The immune complexes were released and denatured by boiling at 100 °C for 10 min in Laemmli buffer (BioRad) containing 5% β-mercaptoethanol. Then, SDS-PAGE separation and Western blot were performed as described.

Fig. 1. Impact of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment on terminal sialylation in different CRC cell models. A, B. Characterization of SLe^x and terminal α2,6-sialylation in COLO205, Caco-2 and SW48OE cells, by flow cytometry (A) and immunofluorescence (B). C. Graphical representation of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac. D, E. Impact of 100 µM 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment on SLe^x and terminal α2,6-sialylation in COLO205, Caco-2 and SW48OE cells measured by flow cytometry (D) and immunofluorescence (E). SLe^x expression was evaluated by CSlex Ab, and α2,6-linked sialic acid was evaluated by SNA binding. Data represent MFI normalized on DMSO. Error bars represent mean ± SD. Scale bar represent 100 µm.

2.10. EGFR cell surface expression assay

Cells treated with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac and Cetuximab were stained with a therapeutic anti-EGFR therapeutic mAb Cetuximab (D1/500, Merck KGaA) for 30 min on ice. Next, cells were washed twice with ice-cold PBS and incubated with anti-human Alexa-Fluor™ 488-conjugated secondary antibody for 30 min at 4 °C. Negative controls were performed by using cells stained only with the secondary antibody. Cells were washed twice, resuspended in FACS buffer, and before image acquisition, 1 µg/mL DAPI was added. Data acquisition was performed using BD LSRFortessa and analysed with the FlowJo software (BD Biosciences).

2.11. Statistical analysis

Quantitative data are presented as mean ± SD of three independent replicates. All statistical analyses, one-way ANOVA and two-way ANOVA, were performed using Prism software (GraphPad Inc.).

3. Results

3.1. 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac modulates α2,3- and α2,6-sialylation in CRC cell models

Three different *RAS* wild-type CRC cell lines were selected as models to investigate the impact of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac on cellular sialylation and EGFR membrane display and activity. For that, we evaluated sialylation levels applying different approaches. SNA binding, using flow cytometry analysis, showed that Caco-2 and SW480E depict significant levels of terminal α2,6-sialylation, whereas COLO205 cells presented no binding (Fig. 1A). These findings were corroborated by immunofluorescence analysis that showed the lack of α2,6-sialylation in COLO205 cells and an intense membrane-restricted signal in Caco-2 and SW480E cells (Fig. 1B). Conversely, SLe^X expression was observed in COLO205 cells and absent in Caco-2 and SW480E cells (Fig. 1A and B). Thus, COLO205 was used as a model to evaluate SLe^X expression (terminal α2,3-sialylation), while Caco-2 and SW480E were selected for their expression of terminal α2,6-sialylation.

Fig. 2. Comparative N-glycofingerprint analysis of COLO205 and Caco-2 cells upon 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment.

N-glycofingerprints of COLO205 (A) and Caco-2 (B) cells were analysed under control conditions (red) and after treatment with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac (dark grey). N-glycofingerprints are displayed as normalized signal intensity (% of total peak height) over migration time (MTU², orthogonally double aligned migration time units). Early migrating peaks correspond predominantly to sialylated N-glycans, whereas later-migrating peaks represent neutral N-glycan species. Treatment induces specific remodelling of N-glycosylation, mainly sialylation, in both cell lines. The level of sialylated N-glycans is decreased by the 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment (downward-pointing arrows), while the level of neutral N-glycans is increased (upward-pointing arrows). * denotes a migration time alignment standard. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

To modulate sialylation in CRC cell lines, the pan-sialyltransferases inhibitor 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac (Fig. 1C) was employed. The treatment induced a significant decrease in the cell surface sialylation profile in all tested CRC cell models. In COLO205 cells, 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment resulted in a marked reduction of SLe^X levels (Fig. 1D and E). In contrast, in Caco-2 and SW480E cells, 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment led to a decrease of α 2,6-sialylation, as demonstrated by diminished SNA binding (Fig. 1D and E). These effects were consistently observed by both flow cytometry and immunofluorescence analyses, confirming that 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac efficiently suppresses the biosynthesis of distinct sialylated glycan structures. Collectively, these results demonstrate that 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac impairs tumour-associated sialylation patterns, such as the expression of SLe^X and α 2,6-sialylation, in the studied CRC cell models.

We next characterized glycosylation alterations applying xCGE-LIF-based *N*-glycofingerprinting. Given that Caco-2 and SW480E cells displayed comparable reductions in terminal α 2,6-sialylation upon inhibitor treatment, Caco-2 was selected as a model for α 2,6-sialylation, and COLO205 cells as a representative model for α 2,3-sialylation (SLe^X-positive) for *N*-glycofingerprinting. *N*-glycofingerprint analysis revealed that 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment induced consistent and profound alterations in the *N*-glycomic landscape of both selected cell lines. As an electrophoretic method, xCGE-LIF separates glycans according to their mass-to-charge ratio and their hydrodynamic volume. Due to the additional charge of the sialic acid, sialylated glycans migrate faster and appear earlier in the *N*-glycofingerprints. Therefore, specifically, a marked reduction in sialylated *N*-glycan species could be easily observed for

both treated cell lines, accompanied by a concomitant increase in neutral *N*-glycan species (Fig. 2A and B). This shift from early to late-migrating glycan species upon treatment is indicative of an effective suppression of Neu5Ac incorporation rather than a general inhibition of *N*-glycan biosynthesis. Notably, 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac induces a general modulation of sialylated tumour-associated *N*-glycosylation in CRC cells.

3.2. Impact of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment on cell motility in CRC cell models

To assess the impact of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment on the malignant properties of cancer cells, we evaluated critical biological parameters associated with increased sialylation in cancer, such as cell viability and cell motility. Treatment with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac showed no statistically significant alterations in cell viability when compared to untreated or DMSO-treated cells, in all the studied CRC cell models (Fig. 3A), suggesting that this compound does not impair cellular metabolic activity at the tested concentration. While this compound does not impact cell viability, the wound healing assay showed that 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment led to a significant impact on the motility capacity of COLO205 and Caco-2 cells, when compared to untreated or DMSO-treated cells. Both CRC cells showed reduced cell motility upon 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment (Fig. 3B). Regarding SW480E cells, no major impact on cell motility was observed. However, we observed that this specific cell model presented a growth pattern incompatible with wound closure, this way being difficult to reach conclusions with this type of analysis (Fig. 3B).

Fig. 3. Biological impact of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment in CRC cell lines.

A. Analysis of cell viability over 72 h of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment in COLO205, Caco-2, and SW480E cells, showing no statistically significant differences. B. Analysis of cell motility, evaluated by wound healing assay, over 48 h of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment, showing a major impact in motility capacity of COLO205 and Caco-2 treated cells compared to controls (untreated and DMSO). Statistical analysis was performed using two-way ANOVA. Statistical significance was defined as * $P \leq 0.05$, ** $P \leq 0.01$.

3.3. Impact of altered sialylation on EGFR expression, activation, and Cetuximab binding

To assess whether inhibition of sialylation can impact EGFR activity, we evaluated EGFR expression and intracytoplasmic phosphorylation, as a readout of receptor activation, in different conditions. Western blot analysis of total EGFR showed no major alterations in expression levels upon treatment in all cell models. In addition, no significant alterations were observed in the activation level of the receptor (Fig. 4A). However, a small reduction in the molecular weight of the receptor was observed in all three cell models upon 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment, suggesting that 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment impacts receptor glycosylation (Fig. 4A). To further dissect the impact of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment specifically in EGFR sialylation, we assessed the SLe^X and terminal α 2,6-sialylation on immunoprecipitated EGFR samples (Fig. 4B, upper panel). Our results showed the lack of SLe^X structures in all tested cell models (Fig. 4B, central panel), and the presence of terminal α 2,6-sialylation in EGFR from Caco-2 and SW480E cells (Fig. 4B, lower panel). Furthermore, EGFR immunoprecipitation showed the specific impact of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment on EGFR α 2,6-sialylation, in both cell lines (Fig. 4B, lower panel).

To determine whether EGFR sialylation status influences a therapeutic antibody's recognition and activation, Cetuximab binding to cell surface EGFR was evaluated. We assessed Cetuximab binding in 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac- and Cetuximab-treated cells, as well as in combined treatment conditions. Our results showed no statistically significant differences in Cetuximab binding in COLO205 cells across all tested conditions (Fig. 4C). In contrast, Caco-2 cells displayed a progressive decrease in Cetuximab binding, with the strongest reduction observed upon combined treatment with Cetuximab and 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac (Fig. 4C), while SW480E cells showed reduced binding only when cells are treated with Cetuximab or in combination (Fig. 4C). Interestingly, a tendency to increase binding to Cetuximab was observed in SW480E cells treated with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac, although no statistical significance was reached. Together, these data revealed cell line-specific effects on Cetuximab binding to EGFR upon sialylation modulation. To assess the effect of different treatments, we performed Western blot analysis of total and phosphorylated EGFR (Fig. 4D). Since it has been demonstrated that long-term Cetuximab treatment affects EGFR expression due to direct impact on receptor recycling [56], we perform a Cetuximab stimuli (4 h prior analysis) to observe the effects of the different treatments directly on receptor activation. This analysis, revealed no major changes in EGFR expression levels and activation in COLO205. In Caco-2 cells, a minor increase in EGFR expression was observed in cells treated with Cetuximab. In contrast, SW480E cells exhibited reduced levels of both total EGFR and phosphorylated EGFR in Cetuximab, and Cetuximab + 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac-treated cells, suggesting altered EGFR regulation upon antibody treatment. Stimuli with EGF did not induce major alterations in expression and activation of EGFR compared to non-stimuli condition (Fig. S1). Collectively, these data indicate that 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac significantly impacts EGFR sialylation, while its effects on Cetuximab binding and EGFR signalling are cell line-dependent, with SW480E cells displaying the most functional effects.

4. Discussion

CRC remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related death worldwide, particularly due to the poor prognosis associated with metastatic disease [1,2]. In this context, Cetuximab, a mAb directed against the receptor tyrosine kinase EGFR, represents an effective therapeutic option for patients with RAS wild-type tumours. However, several patients develop resistance, limiting its long-term therapeutic efficacy [57]. This highlights the urgent need to identify the molecular mechanisms underlying resistance to EGFR-targeted therapies and to develop novel combinatorial strategies capable of improving therapeutic responses.

Aberrant glycosylation is considered a feature of cancer that actively contributes to tumour progression, metastasis, immune evasion, and resistance to therapy [20]. Among tumour-associated glycan alterations, aberrant sialylation is known to be implicated in cancer cell proliferation, invasion, metastasis, and immune escape [30,36,58]. Overexpression of several STs, particularly ST3GalIV and ST6GalI, has been reported in several types of carcinomas, including CRC [19,23,59], and correlates with aggressive disease and poor clinical outcome. For instance, the α 2,3-sialylated epitope SLe^X, primarily added by the sialyltransferases ST3GalIV [25], is particularly relevant in this context as it was demonstrated to play a direct role in metastasis and immune evasion [36]. On the other hand, α 2,6-sialylation, added on *N*-glycans by ST6GalI [29], plays a critical role in the function and biology of glycoproteins, in particular membrane-associated receptors [44]. While previous studies have employed a variety of strategies to modulate sialylation in cell models, including genetic approaches such as knockout or overexpression of specific STs, pharmacological inhibitors have emerged as a particularly promising therapeutic avenue [8,50].

In this study, we investigated the impact of a pan-sialyltransferase inhibitor, 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac, on cancer cell sialylation and on glycosylation-associated malignant properties of CRC cell lines. Additionally, we evaluated its potential as a therapeutic sensitizer to EGFR-targeted therapy. Using three different RAS wild-type CRC cell lines characterized by different glycosylation backgrounds, including an ST6GalI overexpressing cells, we demonstrate that 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac effectively modulates terminal α 2,3-sialylation (SLe^X epitope) and α 2,6-sialylation in *N*-glycans at the cell surface. This result is in line with its description as a general inhibitor of sialylation, and with further reports on its role in inhibiting sialylation, mainly SLe^X, in cancer cells [51]. *N*-glycofingerprint comparison further revealed a global remodelling of the *N*-glycome, with a decrease in sialylated species and a concomitant increase in neutral glycans, indicating that 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac broadly impacts glycosylation beyond individual terminal epitopes. Functionally, inhibition of sialylation significantly impaired CRC cell motility without affecting cell viability, suggesting that alterations in sialylation primarily modulate invasive and migratory phenotypes rather than cell growth. Further, we assessed the impact of altered sialylation on EGFR expression and activation, and the sialylation levels of EGFR. It has been shown that alterations in receptor tyrosine kinase glycosylation modulate receptor activation, trafficking, and downstream signalling, as well as responsiveness to targeted therapies. [17,33]. Treatment with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac did not significantly alter total EGFR expression or phosphorylation levels in CRC cells. However, an electrophoretic shift was observed upon treatment, indicating that EGFR carries sialylated glycans that are directly affected upon cell treatment with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac. Additionally, EGFR immunoprecipitation showed the presence of EGFR glycoforms modified by terminal α 2,6-sialylation in Caco-2 and SW480E cells, and absence of SLe^X on the receptor across all tested cell lines, with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac specifically reducing α 2,6-sialylation. Together, these results showed the capacity of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac in directly modulating EGFR sialylation without a clear impact on receptor expression and activation at the cell level. This raised the hypothesis that inhibiting EGFR sialylation may affect the binding capacity of the therapeutic antibody Cetuximab to EGFR at the cancer cell surface. Indeed, Cetuximab binding and receptor activation were differentially affected across the studied cell lines. COLO205 cells showed no significant changes in Cetuximab binding and EGFR activation, consistent with the apparent lack of sialylation on EGFR. In contrast, SW480E cells exhibited reduced Cetuximab binding and decreased total and phosphorylated EGFR upon antibody treatment, while Caco-2 cells displayed a progressive decrease in binding but no change in signalling. These observations support the hypothesis that α 2,6-sialylation may modulate EGFR expression at the cell surface with direct impact in the responsiveness to Cetuximab in a cell line-dependent manner. Moreover, hyper-sialylation of cancer cells has been shown to weaken the interaction between EGFR and the galectin lattice, at the extracellular domain of the plasma membrane,

(caption on next page)

Fig. 4. Impact of 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment on EGFR expression and Cetuximab binding.

A. Western blot analysis of total and phosphorylated EGFR (pEGFR) expression in COLO205, Caco-2 and SW480E cells, showing a small shift of EGFR molecular weight upon 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment. B. Western blot analysis of immunoprecipitated EGFR (upper panel). Characterization of SLe^x and terminal α2,6-sialylation, by Western blot, on immunoprecipitated EGFR from COLO205, Caco-2 and SW480E cells. Results showed the absence of SLe^x on EGFR in all tested cell lines (middle panel) and the presence of terminal α2,6-sialylation in Caco-2 and SW480E cells (lower panel). A reduced expression of α2,6-sialylation was observed in positive cell lines upon 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treatment (lower panel). C. Flow cytometry analysis of Cetuximab binding in COLO205, Caco-2 and SW480E treated with DMSO (vehicle control), 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac, Cetuximab, or the combined treatment (3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac + Cetuximab). Results show a reduced binding of Cetuximab in Caco-2 and SW480E cells (α2,6-Neu5Ac positive cells) previously treated with Cetuximab and Cetuximab + 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac. A tendency to increase Cetuximab binding was observed in SW480E cells treated with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac. Data represents MFI normalized on DMSO. Error bars represent mean ± SD of 3 independent replicates. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA. Statistical significance was defined as **P* ≤ 0.05, ***P* ≤ 0.01. D. Western blot analysis of total EGFR and pEGFR, in 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac, Cetuximab, and Cetuximab + 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac treated cells after 4 h stimulation with Cetuximab (10 µg/mL). No major alteration can be detected in COLO205 and Caco-2 cells, whereas a decrease in the total and phosphorylated form of EGFR can be seen in SW480E cells upon treatment with the therapeutic antibody.

leading to increased EGFR internalization [60]. Additionally, Cetuximab treatment in ST6GalI overexpressing CRC cells was demonstrated to altered EGFR activation, reduced cell surface receptor availability, and enhanced resistance to Cetuximab toxicity [33].

Interestingly, in SW480E cells, we observed a tendency to an increase in the binding capacity to Cetuximab when cells are treated only with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac, something that was not observed when cells were treated with Cetuximab and 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac in combination. Inhibition of sialylation with 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac may induce EGFR membrane localization and accessibility thereby enhancing the efficacy of Cetuximab treatment, suggesting a possible benefit of treating cancer cells with the sialylation inhibitor before Cetuximab treatment. This strategy may contribute to overcoming resistance mechanisms associated with sialyltransferases upregulation while reflecting the cell-line-specific contributions of α2,6-linked glycans to EGFR accessibility. Further studies should address the impact of cancer treatment based on inhibitors of sialylation on other EGF family members and the overall implications at the cellular and tumour microenvironment levels. In particular, the neighbouring molecular context and membrane interacting partners may have a significant impact on glycan-dependent signalling processes, as well as the binding and accessibility of therapeutic antibodies such as Cetuximab [17].

Overall, our study highlights the critical role of particular EGFR sialylation in regulating receptor behaviour and the implications for Cetuximab therapeutic response in CRC. These findings provide evidence that combining sialyltransferase inhibitors with EGFR-targeted monoclonal antibodies may represent a potential therapeutic strategy to overcome glycosylation-mediated resistance. Future studies investigating the combined effects of sialyltransferase inhibition and Cetuximab on EGFR activation dynamics will be essential to fully elucidate the translational potential of this approach.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

C.A.R., C.G., and J.G. designed the study. J.Gotti, R.V., H.O.D., A.F.C., I.A.-M., and R.B. performed the experiments and collected and analysed the data. C.R., C.G., J.G., and E.R. contributed to the analysis of the data. J.Gotti prepared the original draft of the manuscript, with supervision of C.R., C.G. and J.G. All authors contributed to data interpretation, manuscript revisions and reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Declaration of competing interest

Erdmann Rapp is the founder of glyXera GmbH. Robert Burock was affiliated with glyXera. glyXera provides high performance glyco-analytical products and services and holds several patents for xCGE-LIF-based glycoanalysis. The other authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest with the contents of this article.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbagen.2026.130955>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Glossary

3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac: a fluorinated sialic acid analogue that acts as a pan-sialyltransferase inhibitor by reducing cellular sialylation.

α2,3- and α2,6-sialylation: specific linkages through which sialic acid is attached to galactose residues in glycans, associated with distinct biological effects.

Cetuximab: a therapeutic monoclonal antibody that targets EGFR, and it is used in the treatment of RAS wild-type colorectal cancer.

Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR): a transmembrane receptor tyrosine kinase that regulates cell growth and survival, and it is frequently dysregulated in colorectal

cancer.

Glycosylation: a post-translational modification in which carbohydrates (glycans) are enzymatically attached to proteins or lipids, affecting their structure and biological function.

N-glycosylation: a type of glycosylation in which glycans are attached to asparagine residues of proteins.

Sialic acid (Neu5Ac): *N*-acetylneuraminic acid, the predominant sialic acid in humans, frequently found at the terminal positions of glycans.

Sialylation: A form of glycosylation involving the addition of sialic acid residues to the terminal positions of glycans.

Sialyltransferases: a family of several Golgi-localized enzymes that catalyse the transfer of sialic acid residues from donor substrates (CMP-sialic acid) to glycoproteins and glycolipids during glycan biosynthesis.